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The Leibniz Rule for a finite region
Theorem 0.1. Suppose $f(x, y)$ is a function on the rectangle $R = [a, b] \times [c, d]$ and $\frac{\partial f}{\partial y}(x, y)$ is continuous on R . Then

$$\frac{d}{dy} \int_a^b f(x, y)dx = \int_a^b \frac{\partial f}{\partial y}(x, y)dx$$

Before I give the proof, I want to give you a chance to try to prove it using the following hint: consider the double integral

$$\int_c^y \int_a^b \frac{\partial f}{\partial z}(x, z)dx dz$$

change the order of integration and differentiate both sides of the ensuing equality.

Proof. Go ahead, give it a try.
Come on...
You sure?
Ok, fine.

THE LEIBNIZ RULE

Toxirov Nurbek Xolmirzayevich¹, Xollozov Bekzod Begmatovich²,
Abdullayev Alisher Sa’dullayevich³

^{1,2,3} Termez branch of TSTU named after I. Karimov
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ABSTRACT

In this note, I'll give a quick proof of the Leibniz Rule I mentioned in class (when we computed the more general Gaussian integrals), and I'll also explain the condition needed to apply it to that context (i.e. for infinite regions of integration). A few exercises are also included.

So we start off with the equality the hint gives

$$\frac{d}{dy} \left(\int_c^y \int_a^b \frac{\partial f}{\partial z}(x, z)dx dz \right) = \frac{d}{dy} \left(\int_a^b \int_c^y \frac{\partial f}{\partial z}(x, z)dx dz \right)$$

Then using the fundamental theorem of calculus $\left(d/dt \left(\int_a^t f(x)dx \right) = f(t) \right)$, the left-hand side becomes

$$\int_a^b \frac{\partial f}{\partial y}(x, y)dx$$

Using the other version of the fundamental theorem of calculus

$$\left(\int_a^b F'(x)dx = F(b) - F(a) \right)$$

the right-hand side becomes

d/dy (integral from a to b of (f(x,y) - f(x,c)) dx)

and the second part of the integrand (f(x, c)) is independent of y, so its derivative with respect to y is 0, thus the right-hand side is

d/dy (integral from a to b of f(x,y) dx)

as desired.

Exercise: Using this theorem and the chain rule, prove the more general formula

d/dy integral from g1(y) to g2(y) of f(x,y) dx = integral from g1(y) to g2(y) of partial f/partial y (x,y) dx + g'2(y)

assuming, in addition, that g1 and g2 are differentiable.

Exercise: Compute

integral from 0 to 1 of (x-1)/log x dx

Hint: Define I(alpha) := integral from 0 to 1 of (x^alpha - 1)/log x dx for alpha > 0, and use the Leibniz rule. At some point, you'll

need that lim as alpha approaches 0 of I(alpha) = 0

The Leibniz Rule for an infinite region I just want to give a short comment on applying the formula in the Leibniz rule when the region of integration is infinite. In this case, one can prove a similar result, for example

d/dy integral from 0 to infinity of f(x,y) dx = integral from 0 to infinity of partial f/partial y (x,y) dx

like the one we used in class, but we need to add a condition on f. Basically, we need to make sure that partial f/partial y is well-behaved as x goes to infinity. The condition is the following:

there is a positive function g(x, y) that is integrable, with respect to x, on [0, infinity), for each

y, and such that |partial f/partial y (x,y)| <= g(x,y) for all (x,y).

(In a more general context, this theorem is a corollary of the Lebesgue Dominated Convergence Theorem).

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